

Integrating Sorghum *sudanense* into Silvopastoral Systems: A Climate-Resilient Forage for Mountain Landscapes

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Growing sorghum in the *Terra Fria Transmontana* region

Silvopastoral systems in mountainous Mediterranean regions, such as *Terra Fria Transmontana*, are increasingly vulnerable to climate change due to their heavy dependence on native pastures. Irregular rainfall and prolonged summer droughts compromise both the availability and nutritional quality of these pastures. In this context, integrating resilient crops like Sudan grass (*Sorghum sudanense*) offers a strategic means to enhance the adaptability and long-term sustainability of silvopastoral systems.

Determining the favourable time for sowing is a very sensitive aspect of this crop, since seed germination can be affected by cold or dry conditions after sowing. For this reason, it is recommended that sowing be carried out in spring, from April onwards, with air temperatures above 10°C, and with some predictability that the weather conditions in the following days will not be unfavourable (excessive cold). For earlier sowings, it is advisable to sow more shallowly (warmer soil), and for later sowings to sow a little deeper (wetter area), on average at a depth of 2 to 3cm. Sowing should be done when the soil is damp but sufficiently drained, and the recommended seed dose is 20-30kg/ha. It is also advisable to run a roller over the soil after sowing to ensure better contact with the seeds, level the ground and bury stones. It is a highly palatable plant for animals, it has a high regrowth capacity, and a low level of hydrocyanic acid allows it to be grazed in the younger stages of the plant. Sudan grass, when grazed directly, must be grazed frequently to prevent spindling, and the first use is when the plants reach 40 cm. With the first rains and dews, the plants burst into bloom, allowing the grazing period to be extended, with regrowth ceasing only when temperatures begin to drop with the approach/arrival of autumn.

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